

1 **Properties of sputter-grown CuGaS₂ absorber and CuGaS₂/Cd_{1-x}Zn_xS buffer heterointerface**
2 **for solar cell application**

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1 **ABSTRACT**

2 In realizing wide-bandgap CuGaS₂ (CGS) based solar cells, CGS thin film deposition methods
3 and suitable *n*-type buffer layers need to be studied. Even though CGS belongs to the same
4 chalcopyrite family as the more extensively-studied Cu(In,Ga)Se₂, their different nature of defects
5 and band profile require a different thin-film deposition approach as well as a careful tuning of the
6 band alignment at the *p-n* heterojunction. This study focuses on the material properties of sputter-
7 grown CGS films as absorber layer and the heterointerface between CGS absorber and Cd_{1-x}Zn_xS
8 buffer layer. A moderate amount of Zn is found to be effective in widening the bandgap of the
9 buffer layer while suppressing undesirable absorption loss of high energy photons. An improved
10 optical and structural properties and photocurrent generation are observed from solar cell structure
11 with a sputter-grown CGS absorber with Cd_{1-x}Zn_xS buffer layer.

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14 *Keywords: wide bandgap solar cell, CuGaS₂, sputtering, Cd_{1-x}Zn_xS*

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1 **1. Introduction**

2 A wide bandgap CuGaS₂ (CGS) is one of the promising solutions for low-cost and innovative
3 architectures in solar cells. Owing to its high optical absorption coefficient, it is applicable to
4 various thin-film optoelectronic devices. Research on the synthesis and device application of CGS
5 has been persistent since 1970s, starting from green LEDs [1,2] and more recently to high-
6 efficiency intermediate band solar cells reported by Martí *et al.* [3,4]. CGS is a chalcopyrite family
7 *p*-type semiconductor with a bandgap of 2.4 eV [5]. The Shockley-Queisser limit of a single
8 junction solar cell with a bandgap of 2.4 eV is ~16 %, but its wide bandgap is optimal for an
9 intermediate band solar cell application with a theoretical efficiency of 47 % [4]. This has triggered
10 intense research on both the theoretical and experimental investigations of transition metal doped
11 CGS thin films for intermediate band formation [6,7,8]. Due to its semi-transparency to the visible
12 region of solar spectrum, it could also be applicable to semi-transparent or transparent solar cells
13 and building integrated photovoltaics (BIPV) [9,10].

14 To exploit the potential of CGS solar cell material, deposition technique of high-quality CGS
15 thin films must be established. It may be partly attributed to intrinsic challenges in CGS material
16 property, but like many other wide bandgap counterparts, the growth of CGS has not been studied
17 as extensively as that for Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ (CIGS) [11]. Various growth methods, such as chemical
18 vapor transport [12,13], molecular beam epitaxy (MBE) [14,15], metal-organic chemical vapor
19 deposition (MOCVD) [16,17], spray pyrolysis [18], or electrodeposition [19], have been used to
20 study the optical, structural, and electrical properties of CGS thin films. However, difficulties in
21 controlling binary phase or having residual precursors have been reported, while others have
22 necessitated growth at high temperatures above 850°C and long growth time of more than 15 hours.
23 If high-quality CGS films can be fabricated by sputtering, which is suited for low-cost and large-

1 area mass production, the barrier toward commercially available CGS based solar cells could also
2 be lowered.

3 In addition, appropriate device structures, different from that of CIGS solar cells, should be
4 devised. Although research on CGS intermediate band solar cells is ongoing since Marsen *et al.*
5 published an 1 % power conversion efficiency in CGS solar cell [20], there has been no other
6 reports on their device performance and hence optimization of the device structure is an important
7 step. For instance, device structure optimization has been necessary even for S-based or Ga-rich
8 CIGS solar cells with a bandgap of around 0.5 eV larger than a typical CIGS absorber [11], and a
9 similar work needs to be carried out for CGS solar cells since this bandgap difference with standard
10 CIGS material is well above 1 eV. It has additionally been reported that the *p-n* junction formation
11 mechanism is different between CIGS and CGS solar cells in that the diffusion of a group II
12 element into the absorber's surface or the formation of a *n*-type ordered-defect compound (ODC)
13 are not as favorable in CGS as they may be in CIGS [21,22]. Therefore, optimizing the CGS-buffer
14 layer interface is indispensable to assess the potential of CGS solar cells.

15 The purpose of this work is to study the absorber layer quality of sputter-grown CGS films
16 and to tailor a buffer layer suited for effective carrier transport in CGS solar cells. The CGS films
17 were formed by sulfurizing sputtered CuGa metallic films, and $\text{Cd}_{1-x}\text{Zn}_x\text{S}$ solid solutions were
18 fabricated as buffer layers on CGS absorber layers by chemical bath deposition (CBD) method.
19 While CdS has been a buffer layer conventionally used in thin film solar cells [23], its relatively
20 close bandgap of 2.4 eV to that of CGS is problematic and could cause a significant near bandgap
21 absorption loss [24]. On the other hand, ZnS is transparent in larger spectral range with a bandgap
22 of 3.7 eV [25] and is also better lattice matched to CGS [1,26,27]. In addition, the mismatch in
23 electron affinity between the CGS and the CdS leads to a large energy offset formed at the

1 heterojunction, thus limiting the open-circuit voltage. By substituting Cd with Zn allows to reduce
2 the electron affinity of the buffer layer and hence to improve the conduction band matching.

3 In this work, the optical properties of sputter-grown CGS thin films were studied and
4 appropriate composition of $Cd_{1-x}Zn_xS$ buffer layers on top of the CGS films were also investigated.
5 Photoluminescence (PL), X-ray diffraction (XRD), external quantum efficiency (EQE), and
6 scanning electron microscope (SEM) measurements were conducted to characterize the material
7 properties of CGS and the optimal Zn to Cd mixing ratio for buffer layers.

8 9 **2. Methods**

10 ***2.1 Sample Fabrication***

11 The solar cell structure fabricated in this work is schematically shown in Fig. 1. Except for
12 the buffer layer, each layer was deposited by DC sputtering under the pressure ranging from 0.1
13 to 0.3 Pa. The DC power was 75 W, 100 W, 120 W, and 130 W for $Cu_{30}Ga_{70}$, Cu, ZnO, and ITO
14 targets respectively. For a 700 nm-thick CGS absorber layer, Cu-Ga metallic precursor layer was
15 deposited on a 300 nm-thick Mo coated soda lime glass substrate at room temperature by
16 sequentially sputtering from Cu target and $Cu_{30}Ga_{70}$ target. In-depth composition inhomogeneity
17 was assumed to be resolved by liquid phase mixing during sulfurization process above the melting
18 point of CuGa alloy [28]. A 50 nm-thick GaS was inserted at Mo-CGS interface for an Ohmic
19 contact. The metallic precursor layer was sulfurized in a quartz tubular furnace following the
20 method reported by Fairbrother *et al* [29]. The [Cu]/[Ga] ratio was optimized to 0.8 for *p*-type
21 conductivity while maintaining the chalcopyrite structure and limiting the formation of other
22 secondary phases. For a 50 nm-thick $Cd_{1-x}Zn_xS$ buffer layer deposition, chemical bath deposition
23 (CBD) was used with $CdCl_2$, $ZnCl_2$, thiourea precursors under standard conditions at 70 - 75°C. A

1 50 nm-thick ZnO as a window layer and a 400 nm-thick ITO as a transparent conducting oxide
2 were then sputtered at room temperature and at 200°C using the conditions reported by Fairbrother
3 *et al* [29].
4

5 **2.2 Sample Characterization**

6 For XRD analysis, Phillips X'PERT MPD with a Cu K α wavelength source was used with a
7 grazing angle of 1.1° when measuring the bare CGS film on Mo substrate and 2.5° when measuring
8 entire solar cell structure, respectively. For PL measurements, samples were excited by a 405 nm
9 lead titanium trioxide laser diode (DL-5146-101S) at room temperature in our lab-made setup,
10 measuring the relative intensity with a CCD camera. The incident power was 30 mW. A bandpass
11 filter with a central wavelength of 405 nm and full width at half maximum (FWHM) of 10 nm was
12 placed in front of the laser source, and a lowpass filter of 450 nm was placed in front of the optical
13 fiber connected to CCD camera to eliminate direct signal from the laser. For the cross-sectional
14 SEM analysis, ultra-high resolution scanning electron microscope SU8000 from Hitachi was used.
15 The EQE measurements were performed at room temperature using CEP-1500 Solar Simulator by
16 BunkoKeiki.
17

18 **3. Results and Discussions**

19 PL measurements of the multilayer structure as shown in Fig. 2 depict how the optical
20 properties vary with different buffer layers deposited on CGS. The high excitation energy results
21 in a surface sensitive analysis with an absorption depth of less than 150 nm. The FWHM of the
22 band-to-band transition (BB) band at room temperature became narrower with increasing Zn
23 composition as plotted in Fig. 2 (a). This implies a reduced undesirable absorption near the band

1 edge of CGS as the bandgap of the buffer layer is made larger. This result is consistent with an
2 enhanced J_{sc} and recovery of EQE measured under air-mass (AM) 1.5G bias at shorter
3 wavelengths with increasing Zn as can be seen in Fig. 3. The weak PL peak around 2.54 eV as
4 shown in Fig. 2 (a), which decreases with Zn content can be attributed to BB transition in CdS
5 [30]. Two main peaks were present at 2.4 eV and 1.55 eV, and the peak at 2.4 eV ascribes to BB
6 transition in CGS.

7 The excitation power dependent PL measurement was conducted to understand the nature of
8 the 1.55 eV state. The PL data measured at 30 K from 0.1 mW to 28 mW with a 405 nm laser are
9 shown in Fig. 2 (c), and the integrated PL intensity was fitted to power law $Y_{PL}(I_{exc}) \propto I_{exc}^k$ as
10 shown in Fig. 2 (e) and (f). Integrated PL intensity depends exponentially on the excitation power,
11 and the transition type can be inferred from exponent k value. k equals to 1 for BB transition, less
12 than 1 for FB transition, and less than 2 for excitons when the excitation energy is above the
13 bandgap of the film [21]. The k values of the 1.55 eV band in our samples were less than 1 (Table
14 I). It is thus confirmed that 1.55 eV peak attributes to donor-acceptor (DA) pair or free-to-bound
15 (FB) transition, not to the binary phase like Cu_xS , which could reduce shunt resistance due to its
16 high conductivity. This result is consistent with the XRD results showing no trace of binary phase.

17 The relative PL intensity of 1.55 eV peak emission to that of BB transition was lower in the
18 solar cell samples than in the bare CGS thin film as shown in Fig. 2(b). The PL emission around
19 1.55 eV was previously reported in relations to S poor condition [31], and our studies on CGS
20 films made from sulfide based sputtering showed a similar tendency that 1.55 eV emission tends
21 to intensify when the films were made under S poor condition in a separate experiment though not
22 shown here. One hypothesis is that S from thiourea precursor in CBD process for depositing buffer
23 layers passivates the vacancy defects at CGS surface and as a result reduces PL emission from

1 these states. Better solar cell performance can therefore be expected by fabricating CGS films
2 under S rich condition or conducting a post S treatment.

3 Temperature dependent PL showed an emission peak at 2.1 eV when the temperature was
4 lowered to less than 100 K as shown in Fig. 2 (d). This state was not observed when the temperature
5 was higher than 100 K. The k value of 2.1 eV peak is also less than 1 (Table I), indicating that this
6 state ascribes to either DA or FB transition. Since CGS is p -type, it is likely that shallow state
7 observed at 2.1 eV results from shallow acceptors that are thermally excited to the valence band
8 above 100 K.

9 XRD diffraction in Fig. 4 shows an overall improvement of CGS interface quality with buffer
10 layers. As shown in Fig. 4 (b), FWHM of CGS main diffraction peak from (112) plane became
11 narrower with top layers compared to that of bare CGS on Mo. No diffraction peaks attributed to
12 binary phase (MoS_2 , Cu_2S) or unexpected oxides (Cu_2O , CuO , MoO_3) were present (Fig. 4 (a)).
13 Further analysis is necessary to identify the nature of CdS (101) main peak at 28.14° and ZnS (111)
14 main peak at 28.56° . The trace of ZnO (101) with similar thickness with buffer (~ 50 nm) was
15 present at slightly lower angle under current grazing angle. The absence of the buffer diffraction
16 peak, therefore, may indicate that the film was primarily amorphous in character.

17 The substitution of Cu vacancy (V_{Cu}) by Group II element may account for better crystallinity
18 of CGS and sharper PL peak from CGS BB transition. CGS is known for having significant density
19 of V_{Cu} which is known to be acceptor contributing to intrinsic p -type conductivity of CGS [32]. If
20 V_{Cu} is substituted by Zn rather than Cd, there would be less lattice distortion for ionic radius of
21 Zn^{2+} (74 pm) is closer to that of Cu^+ (77 pm) than that of Cd^{2+} (95 pm). It is thermodynamically
22 more favorable having a lower defect formation energy, to form Zn_{Cu} (0.71 eV) or Zn_{Cu}^+ (-1.68 eV)
23 than Cd_{Cu} (1.31 eV), Cd_{Cu}^+ (-1.23 eV), Ga_{Cu} (2.60 eV), or Ga_{Cu}^+ (1.61 eV) as well [32]. However,

1 we find the differences in the CGS structural quality among different buffer layers are insignificant
2 in our samples under study. It may attribute to low spatial resolution of XRD analyses for a few
3 tens of nm thick CGS film surface below 400-500 nm thick ZnO.

4 Next the Zn:CGS films made by co-sputtering with high [Zn] ratio from 3.8 % to 15 % were
5 fabricated in a separate experiment to investigate possible Zn related defect states that can cause
6 Fermi-level pinning at the interface. Low reaction coefficient of Zn-S than Cd-S and consequently
7 thinner Zn incorporated buffer layer with smaller grain size was considered as a possible cause of
8 photocurrent loss. In CIGS solar cells, it has been reported that the buried junction at CIGS surface
9 leads to its high performance. An *n*-type surface due to either Cd diffusion into CIGS [33] or ODC
10 formation from the defect complex [34] has been proposed to be responsible for buried
11 homojunction at CIGS surface, shifting the *p-n* heterointerface from defect-rich CIGS-CdS
12 interface to CIGS surface. However, neither of *n*-type ODC formation nor *n*-type group II
13 element's donor type defect [32] is favorable in CGS. Such constraints make CGS more
14 susceptible to interface defect than conventional CIGS solar cells, and higher heterointerface
15 quality is expected for equivalent solar cell performances. The PL analysis shows that a new band
16 at 2.1 eV is formed when Zn is incorporated in CGS by co-sputtering from ZnS and CGS targets.
17 Considering the low formation energy of Zn_{Cu} , it could be inferred that group II element's diffusion
18 at the interface may induce Fermi-level pinning. Optimization of device structure and fabrication
19 process are therefore crucial to minimize V_{OC} loss due to Zn diffusion.

20 This work has experimentally shown the photocurrent generation from sputter-grown CGS
21 thin films and clarified the positive effect of Zn incorporation in $Cd_{1-x}Zn_xS$ buffer layers in solar
22 cell structure. The major factor that constrains the solar cell performance currently is the quality
23 of CGS absorber layer. Figure 5 shows the cross-sectional images of the solar cells consisting of

1 Mo/GaS/CGS/buffer/ZnO/ITO layer structure as of Fig. 1. It is clear that the grain size of CGS is
2 inhomogeneous and small compared to the grain size of Ga-poor CIGS film which is typically in
3 μm scale [35], and there exist voids at Mo-CGS interface, interfering the effective carrier transport
4 within CGS bulk and at Mo-CGS interface respectively. Regions surrounded by orange circle are
5 where buffer layers were deposited on the surface of CGS. The coverage of buffer layers of the
6 CGS surface is good as anticipated from the strength of CBD process having good coverage
7 regardless of the substrate roughness. Further optimization of CGS absorber layers and Zn
8 incorporated buffer layers growth based on the results of this work, such as reactive sputtering
9 under S atmosphere and direct sputtering of ZnS above CGS within the same deposition chamber,
10 are currently underway.

11

12 **4. Conclusion**

13 In this work, we experimentally investigated the conditions and properties of sputter-grown
14 CGS for widegap solar cell application. Further, Zn incorporation in $\text{Cd}_{1-x}\text{Zn}_x\text{S}$ buffer for
15 application to CGS solar cells has shown potential for improved photocurrent generation and
16 collection. Hence a better power conversion efficiency can be expected with an improved V_{OC} by
17 using a Zn-rich $\text{Cd}_{1-x}\text{Zn}_x\text{S}$ buffer/CGS absorption layer interface. The main findings of this work
18 are following: (i) x equals to or less than 0.2 is the optimal Zn to Cd ratio for $\text{Cd}_{1-x}\text{Zn}_x\text{S}$ buffer
19 layer on CGS absorber layer, and (ii) Zn is also effective in suppressing intrinsic defect formation
20 in CGS absorber films. With further optimization of CGS absorber layers and Zn incorporated
21 buffer layers growth, first solar cell performance will be characterized in the coming future.

22

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5 **Data Availability**

6 The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon
7 reasonable request.

8

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Figure 1

Schematic CGS/Cd_{1-x}Zn_xS multilayer solar cell structure studied in this work.

Figure 2

(a) PL results at room temperature of Cd_{1-x}Zn_xS buffer solar cells and bare CGS on Mo substrate. Deep defect at 1.55 eV, BB emission from CGS were observed. (b) PL intensity ratio of defect to CGS BB emission. (c) Excitation power dependent PL results at 30 K. Fitting of the integrated intensity to power law shows that both 1.6 eV and 1.55 eV states are either DA or FB transitions.

1 The fitting results of 1.6 eV and 2.1 eV are shown in (e) and (f) respectively. (d) Temperature
2 dependent PL results from 30 to 280 K. PL peak emission at 2.1 eV was observed at temperatures
3 below 100K.

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Figure 3

Measured EQE results for CuGaS₂ multilayer solar cell structure with different Cd_{1-x}Zn_xS buffer layers as of Fig. 1 under air-mass (AM) 1.5G bias.

Figure 4

X-ray diffraction results (a) XRD of CGS multilayer structures with $\text{Cd}_{1-x}\text{Zn}_x\text{S}$ buffer when grazing angle of 2.5° (b) full width at half maximum (FWHM) ratios of CGS (112) plane from CGS multilayer structures to from CGS bare films on Mo substrate.

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Figure 5

Cross sectional SEM image of CGS multilayer structures with $\text{Cd}_{(1-x)}\text{Zn}_x\text{S}$ buffer layer. Mo / GaS 50 nm / CGS 750 nm / $\text{Cd}_{(1-x)}\text{Zn}_x\text{S}$ 50 nm / ZnO 50 nm / ITO 400 nm. The interfaces between CGS and ZnO, where buffer layers reside, are circled in orange. Top images are in scale two times larger than the bottom images. (a) $x = 0$ (b) $x = 0.2$ (c) $x = 0.5$.

	CGS thin film	CGS solar cells with Cd _{1-x} Zn _x S buffer			
		<i>x</i> = 0	<i>x</i> = 0.2	<i>x</i> = 0.5	<i>x</i> = 1.0
<i>k</i> value (1.6 eV)	0.55	0.70	0.59	0.55	0.52
<i>k</i> value (2.1 eV)	0.62	-	0.65	0.61	0.51

Table I

k exponent value in power law of 1.6 eV and 2.1 eV states from excitation power dependent PL.